

OPINION OPEN ACCESS

The Role of Community Science in DNA-Based Biodiversity Monitoring

Carolina Corrales¹

¹Centre for Biodiversity Monitoring and Conservation Research, Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change, Museum Koenig Bonn, Bonn, Germany | ²Department of Invertebrate Zoology and Hydrobiology, University of Lodz, Lodz, Poland | ³Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Information Technologies, University of Primorska, Koper, Slovenia | ⁴Faculty of Environmental Protection, Velenje, Slovenia | ⁵Department of Natural History, NTNU University Museum, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway | ⁶CIBIO, Centro de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Recursos Genéticos, InBIO Laboratório Associado, Campus de Vairão, Universidade do Porto, Vairão, Portugal | ⁷BIOPOLIS Program in Genomics, Biodiversity and Land Planning, CIBIO, Campus de Vairão, Vairão, Portugal | ⁸Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh, Edinburgh, UK | ⁹Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, the Netherlands

Correspondence: Sarah J. Bourlat (s.bourlat@leibniz-lib.de)

Received: 18 March 2025 | **Revised:** 21 August 2025 | **Accepted:** 1 September 2025

Handling Editor: Joanna Freeland

Funding: This work was supported by HORIZON EUROPE Framework Programme (grant no. 101059492); co-funded by the Staatssekretariat für Bildung, Forschung und Innovation under contract numbers 22.00173 and 24.00054 and by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy's Horizon Europe Guarantee Scheme. S.F. was funded by the FCT through the program 'Stimulus of Scientific Employment, Individual Support—3rd Edition' (<https://doi.org/10.54499/2020.03526.CEECIND/CP1601/CP1649/CT0007>). ARISE (Authoritative and Rapid Identification System for Essential Biodiversity Information) is a joint project between Naturalis Biodiversity Center, the University of Amsterdam, the Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute and the University of Twente. It was made possible by a subsidy from the Dutch Research Council (NWO) as part of its National Roadmap for Large-Scale Scientific Infrastructure programme (grant number 2020/ENW/00901156).

Keywords: biodiversity monitoring | community science | DNA-based methods | hobby experts

ABSTRACT

The mutual interest in nature by the general public and scientists has led to many collaborations, past and present. Community science shows great potential for monitoring species occurrences and distributions, especially in combination with scalable and (semi)-automated methods such as DNA-based monitoring, helping to obtain data from a broader geographic and temporal range than would be possible by the scientific community alone. Here, we present an overview of the complementarity between community science and DNA-based biomonitoring through examples from ongoing projects. The involvement of hobby experts is particularly crucial for building up the necessary species reference databases that enable DNA-based monitoring. Based on this overview, we identify some key points related to learning opportunities and participant recognition to maximise the success, impact and benefit of community participants in DNA-based monitoring.

1 | Introduction

Biodiversity loss is occurring rapidly due to several anthropogenically driven factors such as climate change, land-use change, pollution and overexploitation (Pocock et al. 2024; Roy et al. 2024). To address declines in biodiversity, the Convention

on Biological Diversity adopted the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework during COP15, aiming to protect and restore biodiversity by 2030 (Roy et al. 2024; Stammenitz et al. 2024). Achieving these goals relies on biomonitoring, an essential tool to track changes in biodiversity (Backstrom et al. 2024), which provides information on species distributions

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2025 The Author(s). *Molecular Ecology* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

and changes in abundance (Leerhøi et al. 2024) and assesses the efficacy of management interventions and restoration efforts.

However, to have the desired reach and impact, biomonitoring needs to be both massively scaled up by using automated methods as well as carried out not only by scientists, but by a larger cross-section of society as a shared responsibility. Recently, high-tech methods have been developed to complement traditional biomonitoring, such as the use of bioacoustics, camera trapping, drones, sensor networks, imaging spectroscopy, satellite data and DNA-based methods (de Groot et al. 2022; Schweiger and Laliberté 2022; Sheard et al. 2024; Tosa et al. 2021; van Klink et al. 2022; Wägele et al. 2022; Zirngibl et al. 2022). In addition, community science or citizen science (CS) programmes have been developed to enable collaboration networks for carrying out biodiversity surveys (Burian et al. 2023; Chandler et al. 2017; Couton et al. 2023; Johnston et al. 2023; Knudsen et al. 2023; Miya et al. 2022; Moersberger et al. 2024; Pocock et al. 2018; Roy et al. 2024; Suzuki-Ohno et al. 2023; Zhang et al. 2023). We define CS, for our purpose, as the active participation of non-professional volunteers (e.g., Indigenous peoples, local communities and general public) in scientific research and biodiversity monitoring by gathering data and conducting experiments under professional guidance (Johnston et al. 2023; Leerhøi et al. 2024; Pernat et al. 2024; Pocock et al. 2024; Roy et al. 2024; Zhang et al. 2023).

CS has gained popularity in environmental and ecological research projects (Fraisl et al. 2022), as it has great potential for monitoring species occurrences and distributions, along with other biodiversity indicators (Chandler et al. 2017; Pereira et al. 2013), and detecting threats (Pocock et al. 2024) over large spatial and temporal scales (Pernat et al. 2024; Suzuki-Ohno et al. 2023; Tyagi et al. 2023). Moreover, Danielsen et al. (2005) revealed that community monitoring is cheaper than traditional professional monitoring, leading to immediate actions to protect habitats and manage resources more sustainably. Even the Global Biodiversity Framework suggested engaging community scientists in biomonitoring plans to implement and accomplish their goals (Danielsen et al. 2024).

CS participants can have a contributory or a collaborative role (Haklay 2013; Pocock et al. 2018; Senabre Hidalgo et al. 2021). The former refers to sample/data collectors, and the latter involves co-creation CS approaches, which provide a two-way interaction between researchers and CS participants by allowing the latter to be involved in the project design and implementation (Bela et al. 2016; Kelly et al. 2020) (for examples, see Tøttrup et al. 2025). In this manner, CS will transition from an extractive to a reciprocal relationship (Hall et al. 2024). So far, CS contributions to biomonitoring have been mainly restricted to visual observations and the collection of samples and their associated data (Forsblom et al. 2024; Hall et al. 2024; Roy et al. 2024) (Table S1).

Following best practices (Bonney et al. 2009; Chase and Levine 2016; ECSA 2015), CS participation could be extended to (1) volunteers suggesting improvements and proposing questions of most interest to them to contribute to project design and (2) complementing and enriching the role of scientists by assisting in every step of the scientific process, leading to results that

benefit the community (Clarke et al. 2023; Danielsen et al. 2024; Gardiner and Roy 2022; Hall et al. 2024; Leerhøi et al. 2024; Roy et al. 2024; Senabre Hidalgo et al. 2021; Schmeller et al. 2017). The latter is critical when Indigenous peoples and local communities have been involved (McCartney et al. 2023; Tengö et al. 2021), as their knowledge about the ecological systems is valuable and should not be neglected (Hall et al. 2024). Specifically in projects leading to the design of conservation programmes, implementation may be expected to have greater success if they are better understood by the community because they were involved in the process that resulted in the development of a specific regulation, as well as in the monitoring of the conservation action results (McKinley et al. 2017). Furthermore, the more engaged volunteers are in the process, the more likely they are to benefit from any training, leading to more robust data, which in turn will reduce the need for validation and increase satisfaction and motivation to participate.

2 | DNA-Based Methods for Biomonitoring

There are several DNA-based methods (e.g., environmental DNA methylation, shotgun metagenomics, environmental RNA metatranscriptomics and CRISPR-based methods) that could increase the scope of biomonitoring (Ahi and Schenekar 2025; Balard et al. 2024; Curto et al. 2024; Durán-Vinet et al. 2024, 2025; Hempel 2022; Yates et al. 2021). However, metabarcoding is the most commonly used high-throughput sequencing technology for environmental DNA (eDNA) and bulk sample analyses (Lacoursière-Roussel and Deiner 2021; Martins et al. 2019; Meyer et al. 2021; Yu et al. 2012), followed by species-specific detection methods (e.g., quantitative PCR) (Biggs et al. 2015; Feng and Loughheed 2023; Melliti et al. 2025; Osathanunkul 2024). eDNA is the mix of both intra- and extracellular DNA from microbial and macrobial organisms present in an environmental sample such as water, sediment, soil, or air, as well as plant and other surfaces (Lacoursière-Roussel and Deiner 2021; Pawlowski et al. 2020). Bulk samples are mass-collected specimens or community samples (e.g., Malaise traps) used to extract DNA from these organismal pools. These samples have different collection techniques and spatial scales (i.e., bulk samples are collected locally, whereas eDNA can disperse over large distances) that can capture different invertebrate community compositions; hence, it is recommended to use them in parallel (Doloiaras-Laraño et al. 2023; Gleason et al. 2021; Macher et al. 2018; Múrria et al. 2024).

DNA-based methods are reliable and very well established (Handley et al. 2023), yet they are not regularly used by environmental managers and policymakers to monitor populations and species trends nor for conservation actions (Laamanen et al. 2025; Moersberger et al. 2024), except for some European, North American and Australian agencies (e.g., UK Environmental Observation Framework, Fisheries and Oceans Canada, The US Fish and Wildlife Service, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration and the Western Australian Biodiversity Science Institute) that do apply this methodology on an ongoing basis (Altermatt et al. 2025).

It is known that DNA-based methods provide several advantages including (1) identification of understudied, cryptic and

difficult-to-observe species that cannot be detected through conventional monitoring (Cunningham-Eurich et al. 2023; Knudsen et al. 2023; Krehenwinkel et al. 2024; Odah 2024; Zhang et al. 2023), (2) detection of non-indigenous or invasive species (Holman et al. 2019; Larson et al. 2020), (3) taxonomic assignment through reverse taxonomy when morphological identification is difficult or specimens are lacking (Pereira-da-Conceicao et al. 2021), as long as well-curated reference libraries are available, which are almost complete for well-known taxa from the Global North, but still incomplete in biodiversity hotspots or for poorly studied taxa (e.g., nematodes) (see Weigand et al. 2019) and (4) potential to increase the scale, speed and scope of biodiversity monitoring as they tend to deliver fewer errors and reduce processing time compared to morphological identifications, which are user dependent (Pereira-da-Conceicao et al. 2021).

Integrating both DNA-based methods with CS can help address four major obstacles that traditional biodiversity monitoring methods face: (1) the use of invasive methods which are expensive and labour-intensive (Burian et al. 2023; Knudsen et al. 2023; Lynggaard et al. 2019; Zhang et al. 2023); (2) targeting a handful of species compared to total biodiversity, which is often biased towards iconic taxa (Baillie et al. 2008; Hill et al. 2021; Moussy et al. 2022; Schmeller et al. 2017); (3) poor spatial and temporal coverage (Moersberger et al. 2024; Pernat et al. 2024; Roy et al. 2024) and (4) taxonomic gaps (Henter et al. 2016; Macher et al. 2018; McKinley et al. 2017; Odah 2024).

Especially for aquatic ecosystems (Altermatt et al. 2025; DiBattista et al. 2021; Kelly-Quinn et al. 2023; Suter et al. 2023; Zhang et al. 2023), CS has helped professional scientists to cover large sampling/monitoring areas and provide long-term data (Backstrom et al. 2024; Cunningham-Eurich et al. 2023; Knudsen et al. 2023; Suter et al. 2023) or to sample several locations simultaneously to reduce the effect of temporal variations (Agersnap et al. 2022; Stammnitz et al. 2024). Yet, very few studies have combined DNA-based methods with CS approaches (Agersnap et al. 2022; DiBattista 2023; Kelly-Quinn et al. 2023; Knudsen et al. 2023; Leerhøi et al. 2024).

3 | Engaging Community Scientists in DNA-Based Biomonitoring

Nowadays, it has become easier and quicker for the general public to opportunistically contribute to biomonitoring due to the rise of online interactive tools and biodiversity platforms to capture species occurrences in the field in real-time (e.g., [iNaturalist](#), [observation.org](#), [eBird](#) and [Mushroom Observer](#)) (Arazy and Malkinson 2021; Della Rocca et al. 2024; Lemmens et al. 2021; Sheard et al. 2024; Speelman et al. 2023; Uche-Dike et al. 2024; Van Vliet and Moore 2016). Such easy-to-use tools have lowered the participation threshold in CS projects and further increased the potential scale and robustness of biodiversity datasets (e.g., [GBIF](#)). However, the general public is not yet fully aware of the potential of eDNA in biodiversity monitoring (Barbaccia et al. 2025; Clarke et al. 2023).

Agersnap et al. (2022), Biggs et al. (2015), Clarke et al. (2023), Meyer et al. (2021) and Tøttrup et al. (2021), among others,

demonstrated that community scientists can provide high-quality samples for eDNA analyses as long as researchers provide ongoing learning and collaboration opportunities (Bela et al. 2016; Gardiner and Roy 2022). CS projects (Table S1) usually provide educational and interactive training in the form of workshops, webinars, or videos designed to explain the aims of the projects, the sampling and storage instructions, collection of metadata, use of sampling kits and equipment and the difficulties associated with sampling (e.g., air bubble clogging filters) along with the risks they may endure (e.g., bad weather conditions and venomous animals) (Broadhurst et al. 2023; Burian et al. 2023; Clarke et al. 2023; Knudsen et al. 2023; Kvalheim et al. 2024; Meyer et al. 2021; Miya et al. 2022; Moersberger et al. 2024; Shan et al. 2023; Suzuki-Ohno et al. 2023; Tøttrup et al. 2021). Face-to-face training in the field and hands-on activities are also crucial to enhance understanding of the tasks undertaken and facilitate mutual exchange of knowledge and scientific insights (Bela et al. 2016; Clarke et al. 2023; Kasten et al. 2021; Knudsen et al. 2023; Peter et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2023). Follow-up meetings and guidelines can clarify expectations to help maintain participation and trust throughout projects. Social interaction among participants via social media, email/phone consultations, wikis, or further workshops can provide additional opportunities for information exchange and technical assistance (Agersnap et al. 2022; Burian et al. 2023; Sheard et al. 2024).

CS initiatives involve several logistical considerations that should be addressed during the planning process; hence, many recommendations are in place (Bonney 2021; Garcia et al. 2021; Goudeseune et al. 2020; Pateman et al. 2025). For instance, researchers should determine which group they aim to engage (e.g., stakeholders or the general public). Additionally, it is essential to define the geographic scope and sampling locations to avoid biased geographic sampling, establish the sample type/number of replicates, sampling methods and sampling kits to be used and the metadata to be collected (e.g., collection date, collector's name, location, geographical coordinates and sampling method) (Agersnap et al. 2022; Clarke et al. 2023; Leerhøi et al. 2024; Shan et al. 2023). Note that choosing the right preservation method depends on project logistics (e.g., transport procedures) and the methods used for downstream extraction (Agersnap et al. 2022; Meyer et al. 2021; Rodriguez et al. 2025; Seymour et al. 2024). Furthermore, it is important to assess the need for sample collection permits for the participants, the suitability of current databases, and to decide how results will be shared with the public (Meyer et al. 2021; Seymour et al. 2024).

3.1 | Games as a Learning Tool

Games have been designed for training and education (Sandbrook et al. 2015), and they can reinforce the understanding, motivation and active involvement of participants in CS approaches that introduce new methods (Sajan and Sapkota 2024), fostering a learning environment (Othman and Ching 2024). For example, the Biodiversity Genomics Europe (BGE) project has developed and adapted various games (e.g., 'DNA detectives' from Kerr and Breitbart (2021)) to explain the basic concepts of DNA barcoding and the use of genomic tools to monitor biodiversity. Other games available to the public include [BarcodingGO](#), which teaches eDNA and bioinformatic concepts (de Nunes

et al. 2021) and the **Brickopore**, which explains the fundamental concepts and principles of DNA sequencing using LEGO bricks (Boulter et al. 2022). Participating in these games allows CS participants to come into contact with concepts and gain practice articulating them through the scientific method and the projects in development. Participants also gain valuable insights into the methodologies used and take part in creating hypotheses and identifying expected outcomes.

4 | Going Beyond Sampling: Learning Opportunities and Co-Creation

DNA-based sampling methods are straightforward to follow (Altermatt et al. 2025; Bohmann et al. 2014), especially when kits, eDNA CS samplers (e.g., **Smith-Root**) or state-of-the-art drones (Aucone et al. 2023; Geckeler et al. 2025; Kirchgeorg et al. 2024) are provided. CS participants, however, are often unfamiliar with subsequent tasks, such as lab work and data

analyses (Erasmus 2021; Florio et al. 2018; Henter et al. 2016; Steinke et al. 2017; Tosh et al. 2016). Activities extending beyond the collection of samples (Table 1), along with adequate training, are desirable to enhance the volunteers' motivation and learning in molecular biology and to contribute to high-value biodiversity data (Clarke et al. 2023; Kasten et al. 2021; Leerhøi et al. 2024; Wright et al. 2024).

Some institutions, such as the Cold Spring Harbour Laboratory (DNA Learning Centre), natural history museums (NHM) and universities offer CS participants first-hand experience of laboratory work, supporting science literacy (Dopico et al. 2021; Leerhøi et al. 2024; Meyer et al. 2021). For example, Chiovitti et al. (2019) and Wright et al. (2024) trained school teachers in DNA barcoding, Seymour et al. (2024) conducted sessions on standard amplicon library preparation and gel electrophoresis methods for PhD candidates and stakeholders, while Tøttrup et al. (2025) trained high school students on molecular methods for analysing archaeological materials. Before bringing

TABLE 1 | Examples of potential actions undertaken by professional scientists to further engage community scientists beyond sampling.

Action	Considerations
Mentorship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project leaders or PhD students can be role models for CS participants. Consider organising virtual or in-person meetings, and engaging in social media and learning management platforms for educational support and guidance, according to the participants' needs and expectations (Chiovitti et al. 2019; Cho et al. 2021; Polidoro and Clement 2018)
Face-to-face fieldwork	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider producing a short instructional video or introductory reading material to get the necessary background before going to the field (Agersnap et al. 2022; Clarke et al. 2023) Consider producing illustrated guidelines or protocols showing step-by-step procedures to avoid misinterpretations and standardised instructions that can be reused across projects. Translating into distinct languages will allow wider use. Be careful using technical terms. These can be replaced by more common terms, or a glossary can be included (Clarke et al. 2023; Izaguirre 2024) Consider organising a bioblitz-like event to reinforce field methods, involving hobby experts or experienced para-taxonomists or design a 'train the trainers' course if necessary (Biggs et al. 2015; Hupało et al. 2021; Meyer et al. 2019, 2021) Consider partnering with eDNA service providers (e.g., NatureMetrics, SpyGen, Wilderlab, VigiDNA network and SimplexDNA) that already have experience with community eDNA projects, offer sampling strategy designs and sampling training and provide standardised sampling kits (Ayre et al. 2025; Clarke et al. 2023; Roberts et al. 2025)
Training in lab work and data analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement workshops/courses that can provide new skills as well as inspiration to get involved in science (Leerhøi et al. 2024). These can be taught by the project leader, PhD students or educators with molecular biology training (Polidoro and Clement 2018) Take advantage of online resources (e.g., DNA barcoding 101, DNA learning centre, DNA barcoding-Australian Museum, GBIF biodiversity data, EMBL, iBOL and EPA New Zealand) to present new concepts ahead and ensure the same knowledge level, so the focus can be on hands-on exercises. Some of these centres also offer in-person training Consider collaborating with teaching and learning programmes or community science labs to develop your activities (e.g., Wellcome Connecting Science, EMBL science education, DNA learning centre, Gene Technology Access Centre, eDNA Collaborative, Genspace, BioCurious and BioBus) (Seymour et al. 2024) Provide demonstrations showcasing the features of friendly tools, such as the CALeDNA-DNA Explorer, to analyse data (Miyatsu 2023)
Games	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider the use of games to explain scientific concepts, address scientific problems and develop scientific thinking (de Nunes et al. 2021) Produce games with specific goals that are simple, clear and fun, to avoid losing the participant's motivation Consider the preferences and skills of players: Distinct games for distinct levels and publics

5 | CS in the Global-South

participants into a molecular lab, it is essential to ensure proper supervision, provide biosafety training and appropriate personal protective equipment and to use non-toxic products if possible (Dopico et al. 2021). Mobile sequencing labs, including portable labs (e.g., BenthLab and Biomeme) and portable sequencing devices (e.g., MinION) are playing an increasingly important role, as they not only make advanced technology accessible to everyone but also boost the involvement of CS participants in remote genetic surveys by allowing the analyses and self-assessment of their own samples (Stammnitz et al. 2024). Moreover, it is now possible to send samples to commercial laboratories for analysis thanks to falling costs (Clarke et al. 2023). For participants who are interested in understanding all stages of a DNA-based project, a more extensive training could be offered in the form of lectures, including bioinformatics, taxonomic assignment and the use of databases as suggested by Seymour et al. (2024).

One example of a successful co-creation approach is the ‘Original DNA & life’ and the ‘Extreme DNA & life’ projects, based at the NHM of Denmark and the University of Copenhagen, and in collaboration with the Danish National Union of Upper Secondary School Teachers. These pioneering projects that aim to monitor aquatic environments have involved more than 3000 high school students, who collected water samples, prepared eDNA analyses using qPCR methods and conducted data analyses together with teachers and researchers (Leerhøi et al. 2024; Tøttrup et al. 2021). Biology teachers are offered a course on the use of lab equipment and methodologies. Under their guidance, students can conduct lab work independently in one of the local laboratories established by the project at two different high schools. A website was also set up, including all protocols necessary for DNA analysis (<https://snm.dk/da/artikel/dna-paa-forkant>, in Danish). This kind of project proves that public engagement and awareness of biodiversity can be enhanced if eDNA studies are integrated into educational programs (Barbaccia et al. 2025; Meyer et al. 2021).

Co-creation requires established partnerships with different entities/stakeholders, such as environmental agencies, natural history museums, universities, schools, environmental NGOs, conservation charities, hunting associations, fishing clubs, local/national scientific societies and farmers, among others, to promote CS activities and recruit participants, as well as to provide long-term sustainability (Agersnap et al. 2022; Clarke et al. 2023; Leerhøi et al. 2024; Meyer et al. 2021; Tøttrup et al. 2025). Community labs or do-it-yourself biology communities can also be considered for CS approaches as they already have a scientific background and can provide physical laboratories, resources and education (Aldulijan et al. 2025; Eireiner 2025; Landrain et al. 2013). Guasch et al. (2022) and Clarke et al. (2023) suggested some recommendations for co-creation projects, such as understanding and combining local expertise and knowledge, ensuring a wide range of perspectives, obtaining feedback from the CS participants, designing well-structured work sessions and providing different multi-sensory materials (e.g., pictures and videos) to reduce unnecessary mental effort. In addition, Stevens et al. (2014) and Hoyte (2021) provide lessons for researchers and practitioners looking to engage in co-creation approaches with Indigenous communities.

Wealthy countries, such as New Zealand, Australia, the United Kingdom, Denmark and the United States, are leading in the development of innovative CS programmes using eDNA. eDNA studies in the Global South are currently limited, with community scientists mostly contributing occurrence records, while researchers perform eDNA procedures (Belle et al. 2019; Cortelezzi and Paz 2023; Cruz-Cano et al. 2024; Huerlimann et al. 2020; Quilumbaquin et al. 2023; Stephenson et al. 2022; von der Heyden 2023). The application of eDNA in this region faces several challenges, including a lack of funding and expertise, a lack of taxonomic/geographic resolution in databases and inadequate data-sharing practices (Altermatt et al. 2025; Capurso and Stewart 2024; Gonzalez 2023; Stephenson et al. 2022; von der Heyden 2023). The Global North can collaborate and support the Global South by building long-term local capacity and enhancing laboratories and infrastructure (Lopes-Lima et al. 2025; Sahu et al. 2025; von der Heyden 2023). For instance, a collaboration between France and Colombia led to the installation of the first mobile eDNA lab at the Colombian Institute of Marine and Coastal Research (INVEMAR) in 2022, including also training of INVEMAR scientists by SPYGEN teams to carry out eDNA analysis (https://www.vigilife.org/en/mobile_laboratory/, accessed on 5 May 2025). Schmeller et al. (2017) defined a framework for capacity building in biodiversity monitoring that can be put into practice in the Global South.

Another promising CS approach that can contribute to closing biodiversity gaps in the Global South is nature tourism (Martin et al. 2025). Under the guidance of local experts, tourists can have the opportunity to take part in scientific research while simultaneously learning about the biodiversity of the visited locations (Paschoalini Frias et al. 2025). Besides, integrating opportunistic eDNA sampling into tours provides high spatio-temporal resolution and long-term data of monitored species (Rodriguez et al. 2025). Several tourism operators have partnered with eDNA service providers, as well as organisations like IUCN and WWF, to engage tourists in biodiversity monitoring through eDNA sampling across the world. For instance, tourism operators in Peru were involved in the collection of 32 water samples in different Amazon rivers, identifying 250 vertebrate species (<https://www.wwf.org.pe/?361095/Citizen-Science-sustainable-tourism-contributes-to-the-conservation-of-river-dolphins-and-other-aquatic-species-in-Northern-Amazon>, accessed on 5 May 2025). A North American travel agency has provided 78 global samples, which are used to help build the IUCN eBioAtlas database (<https://www.exodustravels.com/insights/venture-out-on-our-citizen-science-departures>, accessed on 13 Aug. 2025), while whale-watching tours in the Azores Islands, Iceland and Italy are involved in the collection of water samples for cetacean monitoring (Barbaccia et al. 2025; Rodriguez et al. 2025).

Community groups (e.g., *Macrolatinos*), local stakeholders, NGOs (e.g., WWF, Earthwatch and WCS) and consortia (e.g., iBOL and CS Network for the Amazon) can help in the integration of CS into DNA-based methods by adapting this tool to local needs, developing sampling kits and standardising sampling protocols and providing long-term funding (Sahu et al. 2025). This, in turn, might become a solution for completing thorough

sampling campaigns in time and space, for collecting specimens to fill gaps in DNA reference libraries and for self-sustainable biomonitoring of remote and inaccessible areas (Huerlimann et al. 2020), empowering local communities to monitor their own biodiversity (Stephenson et al. 2022) (Table S2).

6 | A Special Group of Community Scientists: Hobby Experts and Their Role in Closing Taxonomic Gaps

DNA-based monitoring approaches, especially eDNA, can help fill gaps in species inventories and reduce the reliance on taxonomists (Bohmann et al. 2014; Cortelezzi and Paz 2023). However, these molecular techniques rely on accurate and well-curated DNA barcode reference libraries for species validation, which are developed and improved by taxonomists (Altermatt et al. 2025; Janzen and Hallwachs 2011; Laamanen et al. 2025; Sahu et al. 2025). eDNA has been able to detect new species or cryptic species that have not yet been described because they are morphologically similar to already described species, particularly in biodiversity-rich regions (Mariac et al. 2022; Mena et al. 2021), but misidentifications and deficient taxonomic assignment of OTUs still occur due to poorly curated or incomplete databases (Blackman et al. 2024). Therefore, taxonomists are essential to review and assess the species list produced by eDNA as well as the species occurrence (Blackman et al. 2024; Mena et al. 2021). Without sufficient taxonomic knowledge, the characterisation of biodiversity is precarious, especially when taxonomic assignment at the species level is needed (Apothéloz-Perret-Gentil 2017; Schmeller et al. 2017).

In times of taxonomy expertise decline, hobby experts are indispensable for building the knowledge base around species and biodiversity data. Their often vast knowledge and skills in identifying and recording species occurrences, especially when dealing with local and particular taxonomic groups (Peter et al. 2021; Santaoja 2021; Smith 2024), can exceed that available in the professional sector. They alone are responsible for more than 60% of species discoveries worldwide (Fontaine et al. 2012). Moreover, hobby experts significantly contribute to scientific understanding not only by donating literature and specimen collections to NHMs (Sforzi et al. 2018) but also by providing details of natural history and biographical data (Fontaine et al. 2021; Smith 2024).

CS initiatives led by NHMs and local/national scientific societies could help foster taxonomy, acting as a bridge to provide a common scientific path by (1) training younger naturalists to fill gaps in taxonomy research, and in some cases start a professional path (Peter et al. 2021; Santaoja 2021); (2) training the local community to become para-taxonomists to support biodiversity inventories in their territories (Janzen 2004; Kazmier 2017) and (3) connecting hobby experts with academic taxonomists for collaborations and training in state-of-the-art molecular technologies and novel policies (Fontaine et al. 2021; Lücking 2020; Schmeller et al. 2017; Pearson et al. 2011). Greater involvement of both academic taxonomists and hobby experts in CS initiatives and digital platforms will promote taxonomic knowledge among community scientists, improving their observational and identification skills (Lücking 2020; Mesaglio and Callaghan 2021; Viola et al. 2022). Some projects carried out by

NHMs have already harnessed the taxonomic skills of hobby experts through CS initiatives (e.g., **GBOL I & II**, **ARISE** and **BGE**), whereas others focus on building taxonomic research capacity (e.g., **Barcoding the Broads**, **SPRING**, **EDIT** and **TETTRIs**) (Table S3).

Mentorship within CS initiatives is another alternative that allows transfer of knowledge between younger naturalists/para-taxonomists and experienced taxonomists (European Commission: Joint Research Centre et al. 2024; Schmeller et al. 2017). During mentorships, mentors can (1) provide or improve the faunistic and molecular skills along with critical thinking, communication and literacy skills of the mentees, (2) support and guide mentees through the scientific learning process and (3) increase mentees' motivation (Hargitai et al. 2022; Minocha et al. 2024).

7 | Challenges

Although CS approaches highly benefit biomonitoring, there are still several challenges that may hinder CS project accomplishments:

1. **Sample and data reliability.** There is still concern regarding CS sampling precision and data quality due to the different skills and knowledge of the participants (Kasten et al. 2021), which can cause poor data reliability (e.g., spatial bias due to inadequate sampling design, presence-only data, species bias, false positive errors within species observations and misidentifications) (Callaghan et al. 2023; Crall et al. 2011; Foster-Smith and Evans 2003; Gorleri et al. 2023; Johnston et al. 2023; Pocock et al. 2024; Probert et al. 2022). Tøttrup et al. (2021) suggested that there is an inherent risk of false-positive and false-negative detections, regardless of whether trained staff or a CS participant is performing the eDNA analysis. Polidoro and Clement (2018) suggest that the long-term conservation benefits of CS exceed these potential drawbacks, which can be reduced by having access to in-person training and mentoring, and by providing clear, detailed and standardised protocols matching the project's goals along with data collection equipment (Balázs et al. 2021; Gardiner and Roy 2022).
2. **Human resources and time.** CS projects require both time and experience. Professional scientists would need to dedicate a large amount of time to participate in such initiatives and offer comprehensive guidance, mentoring and training to CS participants (Aldulijan et al. 2025; Schmeller et al. 2017). In return, they will benefit by getting more data, increasing public knowledge of their research and contributing to public education (Tøttrup et al. 2021). Building community partnerships is also time-consuming, but it will lead to opening new collaborations and enabling new research questions (Hallett et al. 2017). Besides, the importance of human interaction in learning and sharing scientific insights cannot be overstated (Seymour et al. 2024).
3. **Funding.** Financial resources are crucial for carrying out CS projects. CS projects can be sponsored by government agencies, national societies and trusts, enterprise/

industrial foundations, private foundations, philanthropic organisations, or Open Science national programmes. Usually, project funding is short- to medium-term and mainly granted to researchers, plus projects focused on CS need to find an appropriate evaluator who understands the concept and use of CS in research (Achenbach 2022; Pateman et al. 2025). However, funding bodies, such as the European Commission, are now committed to funding scientific projects that ‘promote co-creation, co-design, and co-assessment (assisting in monitoring of a project) through the engagement of stakeholders and citizen scientists’ (Arentoft 2023), especially of young people, hard-to-reach groups and vulnerable population groups. Exclusive CS funding initiatives have also been launched, such as the UK Research and Innovation Citizen Science Exploration Grant, or the [Accelerator Impetus](#) that provided funding, training and mentoring to researchers to help them reach the full potential of the project. The Horizon Europe programme recently opened the calls ‘[Strengthening the capacity of citizen science in biodiversity observation](#)’ and the [Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions Citizen for Science](#) to facilitate direct dialogue between science and society and promote community engagement. Additionally, crowdfunding platforms (e.g., [ScienceBooster](#) and [Experiment.com](#)) are a non-traditional funding option that allow project leaders to receive funding from the general public (Sauermaun et al. 2019; Wilson 2019). The webinar ‘[The Citizen Science Funding Landscape](#)’, organised by the TIME4CS consortium, provides further information on the topic (accessed on 8 July 2025).

4. **Protocols’ standardisation.** Sampling protocols should contain detailed and clear step-by-step instructions, as CS participants do not usually have previous experience with eDNA methods (Clarke et al. 2023). Rigorous field hygiene practices, plus negative controls to minimise contamination, also need to be addressed (Seymour et al. 2024). Usually, protocols are standardised according to local or regional needs. A good example is the UNESCO standardised DNA sampling booklet that has been used at 21 World Heritage marine sites across 19 countries (Suominen et al. 2024). This protocol includes information and photos regarding prior preparations to the collecting process, sampling kits, metadata collection and sampling and preservation of water samples. Ideally, specific platforms should be used to collect metadata, such as [PlutoFGO](#) (Abarenkov et al. 2010), [EpiCollect](#) (Aanensen et al. 2009) or [KoBoToolbox](#) (Meyer et al. 2021), which greatly simplify data collection in the field by allowing samples, metadata and photographs to be registered in a standardised manner.
5. **Communication.** DNA-based monitoring methods are complex, and data interpretation requires thorough and clear explanations (Laamanen et al. 2025). Therefore, communication is essential for successful collaborations among parties (i.e., scientists, policymakers, the public and stakeholders) to maintain confidence and trust in the results, manage expectations and make proper management decisions (Hecker et al. 2018; Probert et al. 2022; Toomey 2023), particularly when communicating insights derived from DNA-based survey approaches (see Stein et al. 2024). Projects, protocols and results should always be

presented in the native language, as not everyone is fluent in English. Ideally, complex scientific language should be avoided (Brandt et al. 2022; Frigerio et al. 2021), and both scientific and vernacular names should be used when referring to species (Santaoja 2021). In this way, non-scientists can better understand their surrounding biodiversity and establish a connection with nature (Altermatt et al. 2025; Suzuki-Ohno et al. 2023). It is important to note that eDNA data that originated from indigenous or local communities should adopt CARE principles, and that these communities have the right to keep their data private unless they permit it to be made publicly available (Altermatt et al. 2025).

6. **Sustainability.** Collaborative partnerships with monitoring government agencies or industry, developing science hubs in communal spaces and engagement with other projects or communities are essential to create a sustainable CS approach (Leerhøi et al. 2024; Sauermaun et al. 2020). Biodiversity Observatory Networks can also provide support and link to other biomonitoring projects.
7. **Learning outcomes.** So far, investigations regarding the learning outcomes of the participants are lacking (Brandt et al. 2022; Tøttrup et al. 2021). Yet, surveys, such as retrospective questionnaires, can offer valuable insights into the success of conservation messages and help identify pitfalls in citizen science initiatives by evaluating how the participants’ knowledge and behaviour change after taking part in a CS activity (Barbaccia et al. 2025; Bonicalza et al. 2024).

8 | Recognition

Motivational factors such as curiosity, desire to gain new skills and understand the natural world, or willingness to contribute to scientific research are essential to attract, recruit and retain participants in CS projects (Asingizwe et al. 2020; Broadhurst et al. 2023; Richter et al. 2021). Volunteers do not expect monetary incentives but effort recognition (Asingizwe et al. 2020). Participation in CS projects requires a significant time commitment and endeavour to collect data and specimens when those resources are particularly rare or valuable (Guerrini and Contreras 2020). Hence, giving credit is critical (Meyer et al. 2021). Beyond simple courtesy, recognition can also enhance acknowledgement by non-professional communities (Guerrini and Contreras 2020; Meyer et al. 2021) and also have a positive impact on data sharing (Groom et al. 2017).

Participants may be rewarded with (1) positive feedback, (2) published acknowledgements, (3) free equipment or supplies, (4) volunteer appreciation events and (5) group co-authorship (Guerrini and Contreras 2020; Peter et al. 2021; Ward-Fear et al. 2020). Recognition can also be given to the most active volunteers by inviting them to assist in data analysis or even to manage other community scientists (Gura 2013). Furthermore, sample tracking and explanations of how their contributions were used to produce outputs or decision-making tools should be shared frequently, openly and transparently with participants (Haklay et al. 2021; Hall et al. 2024). A concluding workshop can be designed to provide individual feedback on their performance and acknowledge their valuable contributions (Broadhurst et al. 2023; Meyer et al. 2021; Peter et al. 2021; Suzuki-Ohno et al. 2023).

9 | Conclusion

DNA-based monitoring projects should embrace the potential that CS offers, especially in the Global South, where traditional monitoring can be problematic. Combining community science with DNA-based methods can enhance the temporal and geographic scope of biomonitoring surveys and has been shown to complement the field of taxonomy. CS involvement, along with scientific developments, could greatly enhance our understanding not only of the occurrence, population structure and genetic diversity of different taxa, but also potentially their abundance and their life stages.

DNA-based biodiversity monitoring is rapidly evolving from person-power collecting samples to a collaborative approach, where active participants engage throughout the entire monitoring process, fostering mutual, two-way sharing and co-creation of knowledge, and potentially leading to greater success in the implementation of conservation programmes. Yet, CS engagement should evolve from an effective method to collect large volumes of samples and data to a genuinely collaborative and participatory process that involves co-design, co-analysis and co-discovery, and gaining access to data while prioritising the interests and needs of the communities.

Author Contributions

All authors participated in the conception of this opinion paper. C.C. drafted the manuscript with the help of all authors. Final review and editing by C.C. and S.J.B. All authors have read the manuscript and gave final approval for publication.

Acknowledgements

We thank three anonymous reviewers and the subject editor Dr. Joanna Freeland for their detailed and constructive comments, which helped substantially improve the manuscript. We also thank Ralph Peters and Björn Rulik for their comments on the manuscript. Biodiversity Genomics Europe (grant no. 101059492) is funded by Horizon Europe under the Biodiversity, Circular Economy and Environment call (REA.B.3); co-funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract numbers 22.00173 and 24.00054 and by the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy's Horizon Europe Guarantee Scheme. S.F. was funded by the FCT through the program 'Stimulus of Scientific Employment, Individual Support—3rd Edition' (<https://doi.org/10.54499/2020.03526.CEECI-ND/CP1601/CP1649/CT0007>). ARISE (Authoritative and Rapid Identification System for Essential Biodiversity Information) is a joint project between Naturalis Biodiversity Center, the University of Amsterdam, the Westerdijk Fungal Biodiversity Institute and the University of Twente. It was made possible by a subsidy from the Dutch Research Council (NWO) as part of its National Roadmap for Large-Scale Scientific Infrastructure programme (grant number 2020/ENW/00901156).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

References

- Aanensen, D. M., D. M. Huntley, E. J. Feil, F. al-Own, and B. G. Spratt. 2009. "EpiCollect: Linking Smartphones to Web Applications for Epidemiology, Ecology and Community Data Collection." *PLoS One* 4, no. 9: e6968. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0006968>.
- Abarenkov, K., L. Tedersoo, R. H. Nilsson, et al. 2010. "PlutoF—A Web Based Workbench for Ecological and Taxonomic Research, With an Online Implementation for Fungal ITS Sequences." *Evolutionary Bioinformatics* 6: EBO.S6271. <https://doi.org/10.4137/EBO.S6271>.
- Achenbach, K. 2022. *Funding Citizen Science: Input From the German Funder Community*. COESO. <https://doi.org/10.58079/mzu2>.
- Agersnap, S., E. E. Sigsgaard, M. R. Jensen, et al. 2022. "A National Scale "BioBlitz" Using Citizen Science and eDNA Metabarcoding for Monitoring Coastal Marine Fish." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 9: 824100. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.824100>.
- Ahi, E. P., and T. Schenekar. 2025. "The Promise of Environmental RNA Research Beyond mRNA." *Molecular Ecology* 34, no. 12: e17787. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.17787>.
- Aldulijan, I., L. Scheifele, and M. Mansouri. 2025. "Enterprise Systems Thinking Applied to Community Biology Labs." *Research Directions: Biotechnology Design* 3: e1. <https://doi.org/10.1017/btd.2024.24>.
- Altermatt, F., M. Couton, L. Carraro, et al. 2025. "Utilizing Aquatic Environmental DNA to Address Global Biodiversity Targets." *Nature Reviews Biodiversity* 1, no. 5: 332–346. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44358-025-00044-x>.
- Apothéoz-Perret-Gentil, L. 2017. "Diversity of Foraminifera and Applications of Protist Metabarcoding in Bioindication: Focus on Freshwater Environment." [Doctoral thesis]. <https://archive-ouverte.unige.ch/unige:95588>.
- Arazy, O., and D. Malkinson. 2021. "A Framework of Observer-Based Biases in Citizen Science Biodiversity Monitoring: Semi-Structuring Unstructured Biodiversity Monitoring Protocols." *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 9: 693602. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.693602>.
- Arentoft, M. 2023. "Opening Remarks on the EC Policy and Actions on Citizen Engagement in Research." COESO's International Workshop for Funders: "Solving Societal Challenges with Citizen Science—The Power of Funding." <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ngqb916jRUQ>.
- Asingizwe, D., P. M. Poortvliet, C. J. M. Koenraadt, et al. 2020. "Why (Not) Participate in Citizen Science? Motivational Factors and Barriers to Participate in a Citizen Science Program for Malaria Control in Rwanda." *PLoS One* 15, no. 8: e0237396. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0237396>.
- Aucone, E., S. Kirchgeorg, A. Valentini, L. Pellissier, K. Deiner, and S. Mintchev. 2023. "Drone-Assisted Collection of Environmental DNA From Tree Branches for Biodiversity Monitoring." *Science Robotics* 8, no. 74: eadd5762. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scirobotics.add5762>.
- Ayre, B., D. McNeil, S. Kaminskas, et al. 2025. "Using Citizen Science to Monitor Aquatic Biodiversity Across a Million Square Kilometres." 2nd Australian and New Zealand eDNA Conference, Wellington, New Zealand. <https://ednaconference.com.au/5712>.
- Backstrom, L. J., C. T. Callaghan, N. P. Leseberg, C. Sanderson, R. A. Fuller, and J. E. M. Watson. 2024. "Assessing Adequacy of Citizen Science Datasets for Biodiversity Monitoring." *Ecology and Evolution* 14, no. 2: e10857. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10857>.
- Baillie, J. E. M., B. Collen, R. Amin, et al. 2008. "Toward Monitoring Global Biodiversity." *Conservation Letters* 1, no. 1: 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2008.00009.x>.
- Balard, A., M. Baltazar-Soares, C. Eizaguirre, and M. J. Heckwolf. 2024. "An Epigenetic Toolbox for Conservation Biologists."

- Evolutionary Applications* 17, no. 6: e13699. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eva.13699>.
- Balázs, B., P. Mooney, E. Nováková, L. Bastin, and J. Jokar Arsanjani. 2021. "Data Quality in Citizen Science." In *The Science of Citizen Science*, edited by K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, et al., 139–157. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_8.
- Barbaccia, E., L. K. Rodriguez, B. García Ovide, et al. 2025. "Combining Citizen Science, Environmental DNA, and Whale Watching to Foster Public Engagement in Marine Biodiversity Conservation." *Ocean and Coastal Management* 269: 107827. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2025.107827>.
- Bela, G., T. Peltola, J. C. Young, et al. 2016. "Learning and the Transformative Potential of Citizen Science." *Conservation Biology* 30, no. 5: 990–999. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12762>.
- Belle, C. C., B. C. Stoeckle, and J. Geist. 2019. "Taxonomic and Geographical Representation of Freshwater Environmental DNA Research in Aquatic Conservation." *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 29, no. 11: 1996–2009. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3208>.
- Biggs, J., N. Ewald, A. Valentini, et al. 2015. "Using eDNA to Develop a National Citizen Science-Based Monitoring Programme for the Great Crested Newt (*Triturus cristatus*)." *Biological Conservation* 183: 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2014.11.029>.
- Blackman, R., M. Couton, F. Keck, et al. 2024. "Environmental DNA: The Next Chapter." *Molecular Ecology* 33, no. 11: e17355. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.17355>.
- Bohmann, K., A. Evans, T. Gilbert, et al. 2014. "Environmental DNA for Wildlife Biology and Biodiversity Monitoring." *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 29, no. 6: 358–367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2014.04.003>.
- Bonicalza, S., E. Valsecchi, E. Coppola, V. Catapano, and H. Thatcher. 2024. "Citizen Science in eDNA Monitoring for Mediterranean Monk Seal Conservation." *BMC Ecology and Evolution* 24, no. 1: 148. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12862-024-02338-8>.
- Bonney, R. 2021. "Expanding the Impact of Citizen Science." *Bioscience* 71, no. 5: 448–451. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biab041>.
- Bonney, R., C. B. Cooper, J. Dickinson, et al. 2009. "Citizen Science: A Developing Tool for Expanding Science Knowledge and Scientific Literacy." *Bioscience* 59, no. 11: 977–984. <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2009.59.11.9>.
- Boulter, E., J. Colombelli, R. Henriques, and C. C. Féral. 2022. "The LEGO Brick Road to Open Science and Biotechnology." *Trends in Biotechnology* 40, no. 9: 1073–1087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2022.02.003>.
- Brandt, M., Q. Groom, A. Magro, et al. 2022. "Promoting Scientific Literacy in Evolution Through Citizen Science." *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 289, no. 1980: 20221077. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2022.1077>.
- Broadhurst, H., E. E. Smith, J. M. Jackman, et al. 2023. "Citizen Scientists' Motivation to Participate in Environmental DNA (eDNA) Surveys: A Case Study on Monitoring Mammals in the UK." <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/fa83k>.
- Burian, A., K. Bruce, E. Tovela, et al. 2023. "Merging Two eDNA Metabarcoding Approaches and Citizen-Science-Based Sampling to Facilitate Fish Community Monitoring Along Vast Sub-Saharan Coastlines." *Molecular Ecology Resources* 23, no. 7: 1641–1655. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.13839>.
- Callaghan, C. T., M. Thompson, A. Woods, et al. 2023. "Experimental Evidence That Behavioral Nudges in Citizen Science Projects Can Improve Biodiversity Data." *Bioscience* 73, no. 4: 302–313. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biad012>.
- Capurso, G., and K. A. Stewart. 2024. "Enhancing Biodiversity Monitoring in Mediterranean MPAs: eDNA and Strategic Solutions." In *Monitoring of Mediterranean Coastal Areas: Problems and Measurement Techniques*, 134–143. Firenze University Press. <https://doi.org/10.36253/979-12-215-0556-6.11>.
- Chandler, M., L. See, K. Copas, et al. 2017. "Contribution of Citizen Science Towards International Biodiversity Monitoring." *Biological Conservation* 213: 280–294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2016.09.004>.
- Chase, S. K., and A. Levine. 2016. "A Framework for Evaluating and Designing Citizen Science Programs for Natural Resources Monitoring." *Conservation Biology* 30, no. 3: 456–466. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12697>.
- Chiovitti, A., F. Thorpe, C. Gorman, et al. 2019. "A Citizen Science Model for Implementing Statewide Educational DNA Barcoding." *PLoS One* 14, no. 1: e0208604. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0208604>.
- Cho, H., R. D. Low, H. A. Fischer, and M. Storksdiack. 2021. "The STEM Enhancement in Earth Science 'Mosquito Mappers' Virtual Internship: Outcomes of Place-Based Engagement With Citizen Science." *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 9: 682669. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.682669>.
- Clarke, S. J., E. Long, J. Biggs, et al. 2023. "Co-Design of a Citizen Science Study: Unlocking the Potential of eDNA for Volunteer Freshwater Monitoring." *Ecological Solutions and Evidence* 4, no. 3: e12273. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2688-8319.12273>.
- Cortelezzi, A., and L. E. Paz. 2023. "Macroinvertebrate Biomonitoring in Latin America: Progress and Challenges." *Freshwater Science* 42, no. 2: 204–213. <https://doi.org/10.1086/724732>.
- Couton, M., A. Studer, S. Hürlemann, et al. 2023. "Integrating Citizen Science and Environmental DNA Metabarcoding to Study Biodiversity of Groundwater Amphipods in Switzerland." *Scientific Reports* 13, no. 1: 18097. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-44908-8>.
- Crall, A. W., G. J. Newman, T. J. Stohlgren, K. A. Holfelder, J. Graham, and D. M. Waller. 2011. "Assessing Citizen Science Data Quality: An Invasive Species Case Study." *Conservation Letters* 4, no. 6: 433–442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2011.00196.x>.
- Cruz-Cano, R., M. Kolb, R. A. Saldaña-Vázquez, L. Bretón-Deval, N. Cruz-Cano, and A. Aldama-Cervantes. 2024. "Existing Evidence on the Use of Environmental DNA as an Operational Method for Studying Rivers: A Systematic Map and Thematic Synthesis." *Environmental Evidence* 13, no. 1: 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-024-00325-6>.
- Cunningham-Eurich, I., D. Kontou, M. Yordanova, et al. 2023. "Using Citizen Science Data to Assess the Population Genetic Structure of the Common Yellowjacket Wasp, *Vespula vulgaris*." *Insect Molecular Biology* 32, no. 6: 634–647. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imb.12862>.
- Curto, M., A. Veríssimo, G. Riccioni, et al. 2024. "Improving Whole Biodiversity Monitoring and Discovery With Environmental DNA Metagenomics." *bioRxiv*, 2024.12.17.628643. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.17.628643>.
- Danielsen, F., N. Ali, H. T. Andrianandrasana, et al. 2024. "Involving Citizens in Monitoring the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework." *Nature Sustainability* 7: 1730–1739. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-024-01447-y>.
- Danielsen, F., N. D. Burgess, and A. Balmford. 2005. "Monitoring Matters: Examining the Potential of Locally-Based Approaches." *Biodiversity and Conservation* 14, no. 11: 2507–2542. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-005-8375-0>.
- de Groot, M., M. J. O. Pocock, J. Bonte, P. Fernandez-Conradi, and E. Valdés-Correcher. 2022. "Citizen Science and Monitoring Forest Pests: A Beneficial Alliance?" *Current Forestry Reports* 9, no. 1: 15–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40725-022-00176-9>.

- de Nunes, R., I. de Bem Oliveira, P. Araújo Dias, A. B. Bidinotto, and M. P. de Campos Telles. 2021. "BarcodingGO: A Problem-Based Approach to Teach Concepts Related to Environmental-DNA and Bioinformatics." *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Education* 49, no. 2: 210–215. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bmb.21424>.
- Della Rocca, F., M. Musiani, M. Galaverni, and P. Milanese. 2024. "Improving Online Citizen Science Platforms for Biodiversity Monitoring." *Journal of Biogeography* 51: 2412–2423. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.15000>.
- DiBattista, J. 2023. "Translating Environmental DNA, Validated Citizen Science Data, and Local Knowledge of Fishes Into Meaningful Conservation Action." In *Conference Handbook*, 520. 11th Indo-Pacific Fish Conference (IPFC) and Annual Conference of the Australian Society for Fish Biology. <https://bpb-ap-se2.wpmucdn.com/blogs.auckland.ac.nz/dist/9/608/files/2023/11/HANDBOOK.pdf>.
- DiBattista, J. D., K. M. West, A. C. Hay, J. M. Hughes, A. M. Fowler, and M. A. McGrouther. 2021. "Community-Based Citizen Science Projects can Support the Distributional Monitoring of Fishes." *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 31, no. 12: 3580–3593. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3726>.
- Doloiras-Laraño, A. D., S. Yaegashi, J. M. Serrana, N. Ishitani, and K. Watanabe. 2023. "Comparison of eDNA, Bulk-Sample Metabarcoding, and Morphological Approaches: A Case Study of Riverine Benthic Macroinvertebrate Communities." *bioRxiv*, 2023.05.30.542510. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.05.30.542510>.
- Dopico, E., A. Ardura, Y. J. Borrell, L. Miralles, and E. García-Vázquez. 2021. "Boosting Adults Scientific Literacy With Experiential Learning Practices." *European Journal for Research on the Education and Learning of Adults* 12, no. 2: 223–238. <https://doi.org/10.3384/rela.2000-7426.ojs1717>.
- Durán-Vinet, B., J.-A. L. Stanton, G.-J. Jeunen, et al. 2024. "CRISPR-Based Environmental Biosurveillance Assisted via Artificial Intelligence Design of Guide-RNAs." *bioRxiv*, 2024.12.10.627849. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.10.627849>.
- Durán-Vinet, B., J.-A. L. Stanton, G.-J. Jeunen, et al. 2025. "CRISPR-Based Diagnostics Assisted via Artificial Intelligence: Towards Next-Generation Environmental Biosecurity Monitoring." 2nd Australian and New Zealand eDNA Conference, Wellington, New Zealand. <https://ednaconference.com.au/5539>.
- ECSCA. 2015. "Ten Principles of Citizen Science." <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XPR2N>.
- Eireiner, A. V. 2025. "Extra-Institutional Science: DIY Biologists' Democratization of Scientific Practices and Spaces." *BioSocieties* 20: 419–448. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41292-024-00347-w>.
- Erasmus, D. J. 2021. "DNA Barcoding: A Different Perspective to Introducing Undergraduate Students to DNA Sequence Analysis." *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Education* 49, no. 3: 416–421. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bmb.21492>.
- European Commission: Joint Research Centre, S. Potts, I. Bartomeus, et al. 2024. *Refined Proposal for an EU Pollinator Monitoring Scheme*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/2005545>.
- Feng, W., and S. C. Loughheed. 2023. "Integrating eDNA and Citizen Science Observations to Model Distribution of a Temperate Freshwater Turtle Near Its Northern Range Limit." *PeerJ* 11: e15120. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.15120>.
- Florio, A., N. Rivera, and K. Nolan. 2018. "The Use of DNA Barcoding to Teach Students the Importance of Classifying Biodiversity." *Proceedings of the Association for Biology Laboratory Education* 39: 67.
- Fontaine, B., K. van Achterberg, M. A. Alonso-Zarazaga, et al. 2012. "New Species in the Old World: Europe as a Frontier in Biodiversity Exploration, a Test Bed for 21st Century Taxonomy." *PLoS One* 7, no. 5: e36881. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0036881>.
- Fontaine, C., B. Fontaine, and A.-C. Prévot. 2021. "Do Amateurs and Citizen Science Fill the Gaps Left by Scientists?" *Current Opinion in Insect Science* 46: 83–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cois.2021.03.001>.
- Forsblom, L., M. Azhar, L. J. Barkved, et al. 2024. *Review of Existing and Emerging Techniques for Benthic Habitats*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14099051>.
- Foster-Smith, J., and S. M. Evans. 2003. "The Value of Marine Ecological Data Collected by Volunteers." *Biological Conservation* 113, no. 2: 199–213. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207\(02\)00373-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207(02)00373-7).
- Fraisl, D., G. Hager, B. Bedessem, et al. 2022. "Citizen Science in Environmental and Ecological Sciences." *Nature Reviews Methods Primers* 2, no. 1: 64. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-022-00144-4>.
- Frigerio, D., A. Richter, E. Per, B. Pruse, and K. Vohland. 2021. "Citizen Science in the Natural Sciences." In *The Science of Citizen Science*, edited by K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, et al., 79–96. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_5.
- García, F. S., M. Pelacho, T. Woods, et al. 2021. "Finding What You Need: A Guide to Citizen Science Guidelines." In *The Science of Citizen Science*, edited by K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, et al., 419–437. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_21.
- Gardiner, M. M., and H. E. Roy. 2022. "The Role of Community Science in Entomology." *Annual Review of Entomology* 67, no. 1: 437–456. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-072121-075258>.
- Geckeler, C., S. Kirchgeorg, G. Strunck, et al. 2025. "Field Deployment of BiodivX Drones in the Amazon Rainforest for Biodiversity Monitoring." *IEEE Transactions on Field Robotics* 2: 336–352.
- Gleason, J. E., V. Elbrecht, T. W. A. Braukmann, R. H. Hanner, and K. Cottenie. 2021. "Assessment of Stream Macroinvertebrate Communities With eDNA Is Not Congruent With Tissue-Based Metabarcoding." *Molecular Ecology* 30, no. 13: 3239–3251. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.15597>.
- Gonzalez, M. 2023. "Overcoming Challenges for the Establishment of eDNA Surveys in Colombia [GEO BON Global Conference]." <https://event.fourwaves.com/geobon-2023/abstracts/429fc309-3046-4312-9856-2fd91f0bfd6c>.
- Gorleri, F. C., E. A. Jordan, I. Roesler, D. Monteleone, and J. I. Areta. 2023. "Using Photographic Records to Quantify Accuracy of Bird Identifications in Citizen Science Data." *Ibis* 165, no. 2: 458–471. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ibi.13137>.
- Goudeseune, L., H. Eggermont, Q. J. Groom, et al. 2020. *Citizen Science Toolkit for Biodiversity Scientists*. *BiodivERSA Report*, 44. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3979343>.
- Groom, Q., L. Weatherdon, and I. R. Geijzendorffer. 2017. "Is Citizen Science an Open Science in the Case of Biodiversity Observations?" *Journal of Applied Ecology* 54, no. 2: 612–617. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12767>.
- Guasch, B., A. Amo, M. Hernández, et al. 2022. *Co-Design as a Service: Methodological Guide*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7472449>.
- Guerrini, C. J., and J. L. Contreras. 2020. "Credit for and Control of Research Outputs in Genomic Citizen Science." *Annual Review of Genomics and Human Genetics* 21, no. 1: 465–489. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-genom-083117-021812>.
- Gura, T. 2013. "Citizen Science: Amateur Experts." *Nature* 496, no. 7444: 259–261. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nj7444-259a>.
- Haklay, M. 2013. "Citizen Science and Volunteered Geographic Information: Overview and Typology of Participation." In *Crowdsourcing Geographic Knowledge: Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) in Theory and Practice*, edited by D. Sui, S. Elwood, and M. Goodchild, 105–122. Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4587-2_7.

- Haklay, M., D. Fraisl, B. Greshake Tzovaras, et al. 2021. "Contours of Citizen Science: A Vignette Study." *Royal Society Open Science* 8, no. 8: 202108. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.202108>.
- Hall, D. M., P. M. Avellaneda-Lopez, D. L. Ficklin, J. H. Knouft, and C. Lowry. 2024. "Citizen Silence: Missed Opportunities in Citizen Science." *Bioscience* 74, no. 5: 319–321. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae020>.
- Hallett, L. M., T. L. Morelli, L. R. Gerber, et al. 2017. "Navigating Translational Ecology: Creating Opportunities for Scientist Participation." *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 15, no. 10: 578–586. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1734>.
- Handley, L. L., T. Blackwell, H. A. Broadhurst, et al. 2023. "UK DNA Working Group eDNA Week, January 2022." *Environmental DNA* 5, no. 1: 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.364>.
- Hargitai, E. G., A. Sik, A. Samocz, M. Hathazi, and C. Bogdán. 2022. "Ciência Cidadã Recíproca e de Baixo Para Cima: Recursos Inexplorados de Novas Ideias. Experiências Preliminares de um Programa de Ciência Cidadã Como Envolvimento Público (Bottom-Up and Reciprocal Citizen Science: Untapped Resources of Novel Ideas. Preliminary Experiences of a Citizen Science as Public Engagement Program)." *Revista Lusófona de Estudos Culturais* 9, no. 2: 119–135. <https://doi.org/10.21814/rlec.3996>.
- Hecker, S., M. Luckas, M. Brandt, et al. 2018. "Stories Can Change the World—Citizen Science Communication in Practice." In *Citizen Science*, edited by S. Hecker, M. Haklay, A. Bowser, et al., 445–462. UCL Press; JSTOR. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv550cf2.37>.
- Hempel, C. A. 2022. *Comparing Metagenomics and Total RNA Sequencing for Microbial Identification and Environmental Assessments*. University of Guelph. <https://atrium.lib.uoguelph.ca/server/api/core/bitstreams/73548892-b9fd-4066-b030-8ffb215c252c/content>.
- Henter, H. J., R. Imondi, K. James, D. Spencer, and D. Steinke. 2016. "DNA Barcoding in Diverse Educational Settings: Five Case Studies." *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society, B: Biological Sciences* 371, no. 1702: 20150340. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2015.0340>.
- Hill, M. J., H. M. Greaves, C. D. Sayer, et al. 2021. "Pond Ecology and Conservation: Research Priorities and Knowledge Gaps." *Ecosphere* 12, no. 12: e03853. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.3853>.
- Holman, L. E., M. de Bruyn, S. Creer, G. Carvalho, J. Robidart, and M. Rius. 2019. "Detection of Introduced and Resident Marine Species Using Environmental DNA Metabarcoding of Sediment and Water." *Scientific Reports* 9, no. 1: 11559. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-47899-7>.
- Hoyte, S. 2021. "Co-Designing Extreme Citizen Science Projects in Cameroon: Biodiversity Conservation Led by Local Values and Indigenous Knowledge." In *Geographic Citizen Science Design*, 247–265. UCL Press.
- Huerlimann, R., M. K. Cooper, R. C. Edmunds, et al. 2020. "Enhancing Tropical Conservation and Ecology Research With Aquatic Environmental DNA Methods: An Introduction for Non-Environmental DNA Specialists." *Animal Conservation* 23, no. 6: 632–645. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12583>.
- Hupało, K., M. Majaneva, M. V. Czachur, et al. 2021. "An Urban Blitz With a Twist: Rapid Biodiversity Assessment Using Aquatic Environmental DNA." *Environmental DNA* 3, no. 1: 200–213. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.152>.
- Izaguirre, F. 2024. *The Names of All Wild Things: Field Guides and Environmental Thinking*. West Virginia University. <https://researchrepository.wvu.edu/etd/12463>.
- Janzen, D. H. 2004. "Setting Up Tropical Biodiversity for Conservation Through Non-Damaging Use: Participation by Parataxonomists." *Journal of Applied Ecology* 41, no. 1: 181–187.
- Janzen, D. H., and W. Hallwachs. 2011. "Joining Inventory by Parataxonomists With DNA Barcoding of a Large Complex Tropical Conserved Wildland in Northwestern Costa Rica." *PLoS One* 6, no. 8: e18123. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0018123>.
- Johnston, A., E. Matechou, and E. B. Dennis. 2023. "Outstanding Challenges and Future Directions for Biodiversity Monitoring Using Citizen Science Data." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 14, no. 1: 103–116. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13834>.
- Kasten, P., S. R. Jenkins, and R. A. Christofolletti. 2021. "Participatory Monitoring—A Citizen Science Approach for Coastal Environments." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8: 681969. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.681969>.
- Kazmier, R. M. 2017. *The Parataxonomist Revolution: How a Group of Rural Costa Ricans Discovered 10,000 New Species*. MIT. <https://cmsw.mit.edu/wp/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/371962358-Robin-Kazmier-The-Parataxonomist-Revolution-How-a-Group-of-Rural-Costa-Ricans-Discovered-10-000-New-Species.pdf>.
- Kelly, R., A. Fleming, G. T. Pecl, J. von Gönner, and A. Bonn. 2020. "Citizen Science and Marine Conservation: A Global Review." *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society, B: Biological Sciences* 375, no. 1814: 20190461. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2019.0461>.
- Kelly-Quinn, M., J. N. Biggs, S. Brooks, et al. 2023. "Opportunities, Approaches and Challenges to the Engagement of Citizens in Filling Small Water Body Data Gaps." *Hydrobiologia* 850, no. 15: 3419–3439. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-022-04973-y>.
- Kerr, M., and M. Breitbart. 2021. "DNA Detectives: Outreach Activity Teaching Students to Identify Fish Eggs Using DNA Barcoding." *Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education* 22, no. 1. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jmbe.v22i1.2191>.
- Kirchgeorg, S., J. J. M. Chang, Y. C. A. Ip, et al. 2024. "eProbe: Sampling of Environmental DNA Within Tree Canopies With Drones." *Environmental Science & Technology* 58, no. 37: 16410–16420. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.4c05595>.
- Knudsen, S. W., M. Hesselsoe, M. Rytter, et al. 2023. "Detection of Environmental DNA From Amphibians in Northern Europe Applied in Citizen Science." *Environmental DNA* 5, no. 6: 1429–1448. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.462>.
- Krehenwinkel, H., I. Junk, J. Hans, et al. 2024. "Archived Natural DNA Samplers Reveal Four Decades of Biodiversity Change Across the Tree of Life." <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-5139547/v1>.
- Kvalheim, L., E. Stensrud, H. Knutsen, O. Hyvärinen, and A. Eiler. 2024. "Integration of Citizen Science and eDNA Reveals Novel Ecological Insights for Marine Fish Conservation." *Environmental DNA* 6, no. 4: e584. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.584>.
- Laamanen, T., V. Norros, P. Vihervaara, et al. 2025. "Technology Readiness Level of Biodiversity Monitoring With Molecular Methods—Where Are We on the Road to Routine Implementation?" *Metabarcoding and Metagenomics* 9: e130834. <https://doi.org/10.3897/mbm.9.130834>.
- Lacoursière-Roussel, A., and K. Deiner. 2021. "Environmental DNA Is Not the Tool by Itself." *Journal of Fish Biology* 98, no. 2: 383–386. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfb.14177>.
- Landrain, T., M. Meyer, A. M. Perez, and R. Sussan. 2013. "Do-It-Yourself Biology: Challenges and Promises for an Open Science and Technology Movement." *Systems and Synthetic Biology* 7, no. 3: 115–126. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11693-013-9116-4>.
- Larson, E. R., B. M. Graham, R. Achury, et al. 2020. "From eDNA to Citizen Science: Emerging Tools for the Early Detection of Invasive Species." *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 18, no. 4: 194–202. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2162>.
- Leerhøi, F., M. Rytter, M. R. Lillemark, et al. 2024. "Exploring the Potential of Extreme Citizen Science With Danish High School Students Using Environmental DNA for Marine Monitoring." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 11: 1347298. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2024.1347298>.

- Lemmens, R., V. Antoniou, P. Hummer, and C. Potsiou. 2021. "Citizen Science in the Digital World of Apps." In *The Science of Citizen Science*, edited by K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, et al., 461–474. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_23.
- Lopes-Lima, M., A. Lyet, V. Prié, et al. 2025. "A Stakeholder Empowerment Framework to Advance eDNA Biodiversity Monitoring in Africa: Perspectives From Namibia." *One Earth* 8, no. 4: 101244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2025.101244>.
- Lücking, R. 2020. "Three Challenges to Contemporaneous Taxonomy From a Licheno-Mycological Perspective." *Megataxa* 1, no. 1: 78–103. <https://doi.org/10.11646/megataxa.1.1.16>.
- Lynggaard, C., M. Nielsen, L. Santos-Bay, M. Gastauer, G. Oliveira, and K. Bohmann. 2019. "Vertebrate Diversity Revealed by Metabarcoding of Bulk Arthropod Samples From Tropical Forests." *Environmental DNA* 1, no. 4: 329–341. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.34>.
- Macher, J.-N., A. Vivancos, J. J. Piggott, F. C. Centeno, C. D. Matthaei, and F. Leese. 2018. "Comparison of Environmental DNA and Bulk-Sample Metabarcoding Using Highly Degenerate Cytochrome c Oxidase I Primers." *Molecular Ecology Resources* 18, no. 6: 1456–1468. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12940>.
- Mariac, C., F. Duponchelle, G. Miranda, et al. 2022. "Unveiling Biogeographical Patterns of the Ichthyofauna in the Tuichi Basin, a Biodiversity Hotspot in the Bolivian Amazon, Using Environmental DNA." *PLoS One* 17, no. 1: e0262357. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0262357>.
- Martin, C. J., J. M. Twambaze, and F. Riva. 2025. "A Nature Tourism and Citizen Science Alliance." *Bioscience* 75, no. 5: 358–361. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biaf003>.
- Martins, F. M. S., M. Galhardo, A. F. Filipe, et al. 2019. "Have the Cake and Eat It: Optimizing Nondestructive DNA Metabarcoding of Macroinvertebrate Samples for Freshwater Biomonitoring." *Molecular Ecology Resources* 19, no. 4: 863–876. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.13012>.
- McCartney, A. M., M. A. Head, K. S. Tsosie, et al. 2023. "Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities as Partners in the Sequencing of Global Eukaryotic Biodiversity." *NPJ Biodiversity* 2, no. 1: 8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44185-023-00013-7>.
- McKinley, D. C., A. J. Miller-Rushing, H. L. Ballard, et al. 2017. "Citizen Science Can Improve Conservation Science, Natural Resource Management, and Environmental Protection." *Biological Conservation* 208: 15–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2016.05.015>.
- Mellit, S., M. Vautier, C. Chardon, and S. Jacquet. 2025. "Quantifying Invasion Dynamics: Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction vs. Droplet Digital Polymerase Chain Reaction in Monitoring the Alien Invasive Bloody-Red Shrimp Hemimysis Anomala and Its Interaction With Perch in Lake Geneva." *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods* 23, no. 3: 212–222. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lom3.10666>.
- Mena, J. L., H. Yagui, V. Tejada, et al. 2021. "Environmental DNA Metabarcoding as a Useful Tool for Evaluating Terrestrial Mammal Diversity in Tropical Forests." *Ecological Applications* 31, no. 5: e02335. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2335>.
- Mesaglio, T., and C. T. Callaghan. 2021. "An Overview of the History, Current Contributions and Future Outlook of iNaturalist in Australia." *Wildlife Research* 48, no. 4: 289–303.
- Meyer, R., E. Curd, T. Schweizer, et al. 2019. *The California Environmental DNA "CALeDNA" Program [Preprint]*. University of California. <http://biorxiv.org/lookup/doi/10.1101/503383>.
- Meyer, R., M. M. Ramos, M. Lin, et al. 2021. "The CALeDNA Program: Citizen Scientists and Researchers Inventory California's Biodiversity." *California Agriculture* 75, no. 1: 20–32. <https://doi.org/10.3733/ca.2021a0001>.
- Minocha, T., T. Bhagatwala, G. Mirzoyan, G. S. McDowell, and S. C. Fankhauser. 2024. "Empowering Future Scientists: Mentors Employ Various Strategies to Engage Students in Professional Science Disciplinary Literacy Practices." *bioRxiv*, 2024.03.15.585231. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.03.15.585231>.
- Miya, M., T. Sado, S. Oka, and T. Fukuchi. 2022. "The Use of Citizen Science in Fish eDNA Metabarcoding for Evaluating Regional Biodiversity in a Coastal Marine Region: A Pilot Study." *Metabarcoding and Metagenomics* 6: e80444. <https://doi.org/10.3897/mbmg.6.80444>.
- Miyatsu, R. 2023. "New eDNA Explorer Provides a Powerful New Resource for Conservation." <https://news.ucsc.edu/2023/11/meyer-edna/>.
- Moersberger, H., J. Valdez, J. G. C. Martin, et al. 2024. "Biodiversity Monitoring in Europe: User and Policy Needs." *Conservation Letters* 17: e13038. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.13038>.
- Moussy, C., I. J. Burfield, P. J. Stephenson, et al. 2022. "A Quantitative Global Review of Species Population Monitoring." *Conservation Biology* 36, no. 1: e13721. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13721>.
- Múrria, C., O. S. Wangensteen, S. Somma, et al. 2024. "Taxonomic Accuracy and Complementarity Between Bulk and eDNA Metabarcoding Provides an Alternative to Morphology for Biological Assessment of Freshwater Macroinvertebrates." *Science of the Total Environment* 935: 173243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173243>.
- Odah, M. 2024. "Expanding the Horizons of DNA Barcoding: Mini-Barcodes and Alternative Genes in Biodiversity Assessment." <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202403.0429.v1>.
- Osathanunkul, M. 2024. "Species-Specific eDNA Assay Development for Enhanced Box Jellyfish Risk Management in Coastal Environments." *Science of the Total Environment* 931: 172900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172900>.
- Othman, M. K., and S. K. Ching. 2024. "Gamifying Science Education: How Board Games Enhances Engagement, Motivate and Develop Social Interaction, and Learning." *Education and Information Technologies* 29, no. 18: 24525–24561. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-12818-5>.
- Paschoalini Frias, M., M. Marmontel, A. Andriolo, and H. H. Santos-Prezoto. 2025. "Can Community-Based Ecotourism With the Amazon River Dolphin Contribute to Its Conservation in Brazil?" *Latin American Journal of Aquatic Mammals* 20, no. 1: 3–12. <https://doi.org/10.5597/lajam00351>.
- Pateman, R. M., J. Bennett, A. C. Hilton, et al. 2025. "Opportunities for Microbiology Citizen Science: Lessons Learnt From Three Pilot Projects." *Access Microbiology* 7, no. 4: 000899.v3. <https://doi.org/10.1099/acmi.0.000899.v3>.
- Pawłowski, J., L. Apothéoz-Perret-Gentil, E. Mächler, and F. Altermatt. 2020. "Environmental DNA Applications for Biomonitoring and Bioassessment in Aquatic Ecosystems." <https://doi.org/10.5167/UZH-187800>.
- Pearson, D. L., A. L. Hamilton, and T. L. Erwin. 2011. "Recovery Plan for the Endangered Taxonomy Profession." *Bioscience* 61, no. 1: 58–63. <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2011.61.1.11>.
- Pereira, H. M., S. Ferrier, M. Walters, et al. 2013. "Essential Biodiversity Variables." *Science* 339, no. 6117: 277–278. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1229931>.
- Pereira-da-Conceicao, L., V. Elbrecht, A. Hall, A. Briscoe, H. Barber-James, and B. Price. 2021. "Metabarcoding Unsorted Kick-Samples Facilitates Macroinvertebrate-Based Biomonitoring With Increased Taxonomic Resolution, While Outperforming Environmental DNA." *Environmental DNA* 3, no. 2: 353–371. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.116>.
- Pernat, N., S. Canavan, M. Golivets, et al. 2024. "Overcoming Biodiversity Blindness: Secondary Data in Primary Citizen Science

- Observations." *Ecological Solutions and Evidence* 5, no. 1: e12295. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2688-8319.12295>.
- Peter, M., T. Diekötter, T. Höffler, and K. Kremer. 2021. "Biodiversity Citizen Science: Outcomes for the Participating Citizens." *People and Nature* 3, no. 2: 294–311. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10193>.
- Pocock, M. J. O., T. Adriaens, S. Bertolino, et al. 2024. "Citizen Science Is a Vital Partnership for Invasive Alien Species Management and Research." *iScience* 27, no. 1: 108623. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2023.108623>.
- Pocock, M. J. O., M. Chandler, R. Bonney, et al. 2018. "A Vision for Global Biodiversity Monitoring With Citizen Science." *Advances in Ecological Research* 59: 169–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.aecr.2018.06.003>.
- Polidoro, B., and C. Clement. 2018. "Beyond Citizen Science: Multigenerational Education and Mentoring in Environmental Monitoring—A Case Study." *Integrated Environmental Assessment and Management* 14, no. 4: 521–522. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4043>.
- Probert, A. F., D. Wegmann, L. Volery, et al. 2022. "Identifying, Reducing, and Communicating Uncertainty in Community Science: A Focus on Alien Species." *Biological Invasions* 24, no. 11: 3395–3421. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-022-02858-8>.
- Quilumbaquin, W., A. Carrera-Gonzalez, C. Van der Heyden, and H. M. Ortega-Andrade. 2023. "Environmental DNA and Visual Encounter Surveys for Amphibian Biomonitoring in Aquatic Environments of the Ecuadorian Amazon." *PeerJ* 11: e15455. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.15455>.
- Richter, A., O. Comay, C. S. Svenningsen, et al. 2021. "Motivation and Support Services in Citizen Science Insect Monitoring: A Cross-Country Study." *Biological Conservation* 263: 109325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2021.109325>.
- Roberts, H., A. Weeks, S. Marwood, et al. 2025. "The Great Australian Wildlife Search: Large-Scale Biodiversity Assessments Using eDNA Metabarcoding and Citizen Scientists." 2nd Australian and New Zealand eDNA Conference, Wellington, New Zealand. <https://ednac.onference.com.au/5694>.
- Rodriguez, L. K., B. García Ovide, E. Barbaccia, et al. 2025. "Enhancing Environmental DNA Sampling Efficiency for Cetacean Detection on Whale Watching Tours." *Environmental DNA* 7, no. 3: e70103. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.70103>.
- Roy, H. E., A. F. Martinou, M. J. O. Pocock, V. Werenkraut, and D. B. Roy. 2024. "The Global Reach of Citizen Science for Monitoring Insects." *One Earth* 7, no. 4: 552–557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2024.03.009>.
- Sahu, A., M. Singh, R. K. Laxmi, T. K. Shah, and M. Sharma. 2025. "Environmental DNA (eDNA): An Eco-Friendly Approach for Conservation of Indian Freshwater Diversity—A Review." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 32, no. 15: 9333–9360. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-025-36202-z>.
- Sajan, K. C., and A. Sapkota. 2024. "Can Gamification Save the Planet? Revolutionizing Citizen Science for Biodiversity Conservation." <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5008056>.
- Sandbrook, C., W. M. Adams, and B. Monteferrri. 2015. "Digital Games and Biodiversity Conservation." *Conservation Letters* 8, no. 2: 118–124. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12113>.
- Santaoja, M. 2021. *Insect Affects: A Study on the Motivations of Amateur Entomologists and Implications for Citizen Science*. Science & Technology Studies. <https://doi.org/10.23987/sts.107703>.
- Sauermann, H., C. Franzoni, and K. Shafi. 2019. "Crowdfunding Scientific Research: Descriptive Insights and Correlates of Funding Success." *PLoS One* 14, no. 1: e0208384. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0208384>.
- Sauermann, H., K. Vohland, V. Antoniou, et al. 2020. "Citizen Science and Sustainability Transitions." *Research Policy* 49, no. 5: 103978. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.103978>.
- Schmeller, D. S., M. Böhm, C. Arvanitidis, et al. 2017. "Building Capacity in Biodiversity Monitoring at the Global Scale." *Biodiversity and Conservation* 26, no. 12: 2765–2790. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-017-1388-7>.
- Schweiger, A. K., and E. Laliberté. 2022. "Plant Beta-Diversity Across Biomes Captured by Imaging Spectroscopy." *Nature Communications* 13, no. 1: 2767. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-30369-6>.
- Senabre Hidalgo, E., J. Perelló, F. Becker, I. Bonhoure, M. Legris, and A. Cigarini. 2021. "Participation and co-Creation in Citizen Science." In *The Science of Citizen Science*, edited by K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, et al., 199–218. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_11.
- Seymour, M., I. Guibert, G.-J. Jeunen, et al. 2024. "The First International eDNA Workshop in Hong Kong: A Beginner's Guide for the Next-Generation eDNA Researcher." *Environmental DNA* 6, no. 3: e552. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.552>.
- Sforzi, A., J. Tweddle, J. Vogel, et al. 2018. "Citizen Science and the Role of Natural History Museums." In *Citizen Science*, edited by J. Vogel, Z. Makuch, S. Hecker, M. Haklay, A. Bowser, and A. Bonn, 429–444. UCL Press; JSTOR. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv550cf2.36>.
- Shan, J., Y. Jia, P. Hickenbotham, L. Teulière, and M. R. J. Clokie. 2023. "Combining Citizen Science and Molecular Diagnostic Methods to Investigate the Prevalence of *Borrelia burgdorferi* s.l. and *Borrelia miyamotoi* in Tick Pools Across Great Britain." *Frontiers in Microbiology* 14: 2023. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/microbiology/articles/10.3389/fmicb.2023.1126498>.
- Sheard, J. K., T. Adriaens, D. E. Bowler, et al. 2024. "Emerging Technologies in Citizen Science and Potential for Insect Monitoring." *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society, B: Biological Sciences* 379, no. 1904: 20230106. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2023.0106>.
- Smith, N. E. C. 2024. "Messy Databases: Recognizing Transcribers as Experts and Engaging Amateur Naturalists in Digitization." *Curator: The Museum Journal* 67, no. 3: 725–732. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cura.12616>.
- Speelman, E. N., E. Escano, D. Marcos, and N. Becu. 2023. "Serious Games and Citizen Science; From Parallel Pathways to Greater Synergies." *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 64: 101320.
- Stammnitz, M. R., A. Hartman Scholz, and D. J. Duffy. 2024. "Environmental DNA Without Borders: Let's Embrace Decentralised Genomics to Meet the UN's Biodiversity Targets." *EMBO Reports* 25, no. 10: 4095–4099. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44319-024-00264-w>.
- Stein, E. D., C. L. Jerde, E. A. Allan, et al. 2024. "Critical Considerations for Communicating Environmental DNA Science." *Environmental DNA* 6, no. 1: e472. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.472>.
- Steinke, D., V. Breton, E. Berzitis, and P. D. N. Hebert. 2017. "The School Malaise Trap Program: Coupling Educational Outreach With Scientific Discovery." *PLoS Biology* 15, no. 4: e2001829. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001829>.
- Stephenson, P. J., M. C. Londoño-Murcia, P. A. V. Borges, et al. 2022. "Measuring the Impact of Conservation: The Growing Importance of Monitoring Fauna, Flora and Funga." *Diversity* 14, no. 10: 824. <https://doi.org/10.3390/d14100824>.
- Stevens, M., M. Vitos, J. Altenbuchner, G. Conquest, J. Lewis, and M. Haklay. 2014. "Taking Participatory Citizen Science to Extremes." *IEEE Pervasive Computing* 13, no. 2: 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MPRV.2014.37>.

- Suominen, S., P. Provoost, S. Principe, et al. 2024. *Engaging Communities to Safeguard Ocean Life: UNESCO Environmental DNA Expeditions*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.58337/CBXU3518>.
- Suter, S., B. Barrett, and N. Welden. 2023. "Do Biodiversity Monitoring Citizen Science Surveys Meet the Core Principles of Open Science Practices?" *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 195, no. 2: 295. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-022-10887-y>.
- Suzuki-Ohno, Y., A. S. Tanabe, A. Kasai, et al. 2023. "Evaluation of Community Science Monitoring With Environmental DNA for Marine Fish Species: 'Fish Survey Project Using Environmental DNA'." *Environmental DNA* 5, no. 3: 613–623. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.425>.
- Tengö, M., B. J. Austin, F. Danielsen, and Á. Fernández-Llamazares. 2021. "Creating Synergies Between Citizen Science and Indigenous and Local Knowledge." *Bioscience* 71, no. 5: 503–518. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biab023>.
- Toomey, A. H. 2023. "Why Facts Don't Change Minds: Insights From Cognitive Science for the Improved Communication of Conservation Research." *Biological Conservation* 278: 109886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109886>.
- Tosa, M. I., E. H. Dzedzic, C. L. Appel, et al. 2021. "The Rapid Rise of Next-Generation Natural History." *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 9: 698131. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.698131>.
- Tosh, J., K. James, F. Rumsey, A. Crookshank, R. Dyer, and D. Hopkins. 2016. "Is DNA Barcoding Child's Play? Science Education and the Utility of DNA Barcoding for the Discrimination of UK Tree Species." *Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society* 181, no. 4: 711–722. <https://doi.org/10.1111/boj.12449>.
- Tøttrup, A. P., M. R. Lillemark, J. Hansen, et al. 2025. "A Concept for Co-Creation in Participatory Science: Insights From Developing the Archaeological Next Generation Lab." *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice* 10: 22. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.832>.
- Tøttrup, A. P., L. Svenningsen, M. Rytter, M. R. Lillemark, P. Møller, and S. W. Knudsen. 2021. "Citizens in the Lab: Performance and Validation of eDNA Results." *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice* 6, no. 1: 35. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.382>.
- Tyagi, A., M. Godbole, A. T. Vanak, and U. Ramakrishnan. 2023. "Citizen Science Facilitates First Ever Genetic Detection of Wolf-Dog Hybridization in Indian Savannahs." *Ecology and Evolution* 13, no. 5: e10100. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10100>.
- Uche-Dike, R., E. Tolman, C. Benischek, et al. 2024. "Environmental DNA vs. Community Science: Strengths and Limitations for Urban Odonata Surveys." *bioRxiv*, 2024.11.26.625270. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.11.26.625270>.
- van Klink, R., T. August, Y. Bas, et al. 2022. "Emerging Technologies Revolutionise Insect Ecology and Monitoring." *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 37, no. 10: 872–885. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2022.06.001>.
- Van Vliet, K., and C. Moore. 2016. "Citizen Science Initiatives: Engaging the Public and Demystifying Science." *Journal of Microbiology & Biology Education* 17, no. 1: 13–16. <https://doi.org/10.1128/jmbe.v17i1.1019>.
- Viola, B. M., K. J. Sorrell, R. H. Clarke, S. P. Corney, and P. M. Vaughan. 2022. "Amateurs Can Be Experts: A New Perspective on Collaborations With Citizen Scientists." *Biological Conservation* 274: 109739. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109739>.
- von der Heyden, S. 2023. "Environmental DNA Surveys of African Biodiversity: State of Knowledge, Challenges, and Opportunities." *Environmental DNA* 5, no. 1: 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/edn3.363>.
- Wägele, J. W., P. Bodesheim, S. J. Bourlat, et al. 2022. "Towards a Multisensor Station for Automated Biodiversity Monitoring." *Basic and Applied Ecology* 59: 105–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2022.01.003>.
- Ward-Fear, G., G. B. Pauly, J. E. Vendetti, and R. Shine. 2020. "Authorship Protocols Must Change to Credit Citizen Scientists." *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 35, no. 3: 187–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2019.10.007>.
- Weigand, H., A. J. Beermann, F. Čiampor, et al. 2019. "DNA Barcode Reference Libraries for the Monitoring of Aquatic Biota in Europe: Gap-Analysis and Recommendations for Future Work." *Science of the Total Environment* 678: 499–524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.04.247>.
- Wilson, M. A. 2019. "Crowdfunding Science." *Genome Biology* 20, no. 1: 250. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-019-1864-3>.
- Wright, L., J. Garbarino, and C. Marizzi. 2024. "Engaging Students and Teachers as Community Scientists in DNA Barcoding Initiatives." In *DNA Barcoding: Methods and Protocols*, edited by R. DeSalle, 525–535. Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-3581-0_32.
- Yates, M. C., A. M. Derry, and M. E. Cristescu. 2021. "Environmental RNA: A Revolution in Ecological Resolution?" *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 36, no. 7: 601–609. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2021.03.001>.
- Yu, D. W., Y. Ji, B. C. Emerson, et al. 2012. "Biodiversity Soup: Metabarcoding of Arthropods for Rapid Biodiversity Assessment and Biomonitoring." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 3, no. 4: 613–623. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041-210X.2012.00198.x>.
- Zhang, H., J. Yang, L. Zhang, X. Gu, and X. Zhang. 2023. "Citizen Science Meets eDNA: A New Boom in Research Exploring Urban Wetland Biodiversity." *Environmental Science and Ecotechnology* 16: 100275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.es.2023.100275>.
- Zirngibl, M., U. von Ammon, X. Pochon, and A. Zaiko. 2022. "A Rapid Molecular Assay for Detecting the Mediterranean Fanworm *Sabella spallanzanii* Trialed by Non-Scientist Users." *Frontiers in Marine Science* 9: 861657. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.861657>.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Table S1:** Examples of DNA-based monitoring projects that have successfully engaged CS participants in fieldwork, either by collecting individual specimens or eDNA/bulk samples. **Table S2:** Examples of projects that could engage community scientists in monitoring using DNA-based methods in Latin America. **Table S3:** Examples of European projects that have benefited from the help of hobby experts.